

DIC Deformation Measurement in Cracked CFRP Cross-ply Laminates

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INTRODUCTION

Damages in CFRP laminates

- CFRP exhibit various competing damage modes: Matrix cracks, delamination, fiber breakage & etc.
- Initial damage: **Matrix intralaminar cracks** (usually in off-axis plies)
- Delamination, oblique & curve cracks** are considered as secondary mode damages in laminates

CFRP angle-ply [0/45₁₂/0] laminate

Schematic of the matrix crack pattern in CFRP [0₄/90₂₄]_s laminate

Objective

To measure the mechanical deformation around the damages in cross-ply CFRP laminates by using **Digital Image Correlation (DIC)**

- Strain distribution observation around the existed cracks from:
 - Surface direction
 - Thickness direction
- Secondary mode damages observation
 - Oblique cracks
 - Curved cracks

Digital Image Correlation (DIC)

METHOD & MATERIAL

Material

Material	CFRP prepreg, 0.15 mm/ply
Prepreg type	T700SC/2592, Torayca
Structures	[0/90 ₄] _s , [0/90 ₆] _s , [0 ₄ /90 ₂₄] _s
Curing	Autoclave (130°C, 0.2MPa)

Autoclave

Specimen measurement

Tensile device: Shimadzu AG-X Plus, Cross-head speed: 1 mm/min

DIC Strain deformation measurement

Schematic figure of DIC setting

Software:

- GOM ARAMIS
- Measuring conditions:
 - Sensor: ARAMIS 5M
 - Resolution: 2448X2050 Pixels
 - Lens: Titanar 75mm
 - Frame frequency: 0.5 Hz
 - Measuring volume: 35X29
 - Calibration panel: CQ/CP20

RESULT & DISCUSSION

Observation from surface direction

X-ray radiograph of cracked cross-ply [0/90₆]_s laminates

DIC strain distribution from surface direction

Plotted strain distribution along the specimen

Observation from thickness direction

Strain distribution from thickness direction of [0₄/90₂₄]_s laminate

Schematic of the matrix crack pattern in [0₄/90₂₄]_s laminate

X-ray radiograph of artificially cracked [0₄/90₄₈]_s laminate

Specimen's edge observation of fractured [0₄/90₂₄]_s laminate

DIC shear strain distribution from the thickness direction at earlier stages

(Stage where oblique and curved cracks have not yet occurred)

Strain distribution in loading direction

Shear strain distribution

Plotted shear strain distribution

Comparison with DIC image with oblique & curved cracks

- Area with highest shear strain → Biggest possibility of the initiation of the oblique cracks
- The area with larger distribution of shear strain is said to have higher accumulation of maximum principle stress [1]
- Curved cracks: Formed when two oblique cracks propagated from opposite side of each other, meet & combine to become a curved shape near to the existed straight crack

[1] Jalalvand M., et al. Composites: Part A Vol. 67 (2014) pp.140–148

y : Loading direction
x : Width (straight transverse cracks) direction
z : Thickness direction